

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS. PART II

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It has been observed that for the solutions of the same solute in different solvents, the effect of heating is different. It is suggested that solutions contain particles which act as adsorbents and adsorb solute. During the process of heating these solute particles go into the solution and hence heating effect is observed. Further, for the solutions of the same solute in different solvents amount of solute adsorbed is different, and hence heating effect is different. In solutions where no solute is adsorbed by the adsorbate, heating effect is not observed. This hypothesis is supported by the experimental results obtained on the adsorption of different solutes by bone charcoal from the solutions, in different solvents.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 94) it has been observed that the effect of heating is different for the solutions of the same solute in different solvents. No explanation was suggested for this behaviour. In the present paper an attempt has been made to explain this behaviour by the adsorption hypothesis of Richards (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 482) and Richards, Kirkpatrick and Hutz (*ibid.*, 1936, 58, 2243). According to Richards liquid may be supposed to contain particles which may act as adsorbents and adsorb liquid or the solid crystals depending upon the previous treatment. Thus, if some crystalline particles are adsorbed by the adsorbate and do not go into the melt during the process of heating, then these adsorbed crystals will help in the process of crystallisation in the supercooled region of the melt. If the substance is heated much above its melting point, then the adsorbed crystals on the surface of the adsorbate melt and the adsorbate also loses its activity of forming crystal nuclei and the melt shows heating effect.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental method for determining adsorption will be published elsewhere. Experimental work has been done by one of the authors (R. D. S.) on the adsorption of the same solute from the solutions in different solvents by bone charcoal. A summary of the results obtained is given in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Solute.	Sorption (m. moles/litre).	T°.	Temperature of crystallisation.			Remark.
CCl ₄	Naphthalene	29.3	50°	46.5°	46.5°	47.0°	No heating
Toluene	" "	17.4	55°	48.5°	48.0°	48.2°	Do
Chlorobenzene	" "	17.3	55°	51.0°	51.0°	51.5°	Do
Benzene	" "	30.5	55°	49.4°	48.5°	48.0°	Little heating
n-BuOH	" "	122.8	55°	42.0°	39.5°	36.0°	Heating
EtOH	" "	110.3	55°	48.2°	43.4°	44.0°	Do
n-PrOH	" "	96.6	55°	48.5°	39.0°	42.0°	Do
MeOH	" "	79.6	50°	46.0°	45.0°	45.0°	Little heating
Acetic acid	" "	59.1	50°	43.5°	36.5°	35.5°	Heating
Nitrobenzene	Benzoic acid	29.9	—	39.4°	39.4°	39.5°	No heating
Acetone	" "	42.3	57°	44.4°	37.6°	35.0°	Heating
m-Xylene	" "	45.0	55°	53.0°	51.6°	50.5°	Do
Toluene	" "	53.7	55°	36.0°	35.0°	33.0°	Do
Benzene	" "	66.9	55°	47.0°	45.0°	42.0°	Do
o-Xylene	" "	83.5	—	54.2°	42.0°	48.0°	Do
CCl ₄	" "	103.0	—	48.6°	45.8°	45.2°	Do

From the results given it is observed that in solutions where the adsorption is high, heating effect is observed. Probably it is due to the fact that in supersaturated solutions the particles of solute are adsorbed by adsorbate in crystalline state and they do not go into solution. When a clear solution is observed, even then a few solute particles remain in the adsorbate. As the solution is cooled below the saturation temperature, adsorbed solid crystals grow and form large crystals. But if the solution is heated for a long time above its saturation temperature, the adsorbed crystals dissolve and thus the adsorbate loses its activity of starting the process of crystallisation and hence $(T_s - T)$ increases with the frequency of heating and cooling. Once these adsorbed crystals get out of the adsorbate, it takes long time for rearrangement.

This hypothesis explains the phenomenon of heating effect in solution as well as in the different solutions of the same solute having different amounts of heating effect.

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